

ECOLOGICAL PROBLEMS AND METHODS OF ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION.

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Abstract: *This study discusses environmental emergency situations that are likely to occur in the territory of our country, prevention of such emergency situations, their elimination, protection of the population and our territories from them.*

Key words: *Water resources, Aral Sea, botany, zoology, microbiology, chemistry, soil science, plant science, biosphere.*

Introduction: In ancient times, people lived in a wild way, but later, from the time of living in tribes, they began to exert pressure on nature. At present, human thinking has developed so deeply that over the last century, energy resources have increased a hundred times, and the level of armaments has increased by a million times. Of course, such a situation will have a negative impact on our mother planet and the environment.

Although mother nature surprises us all with its beauty and freshness and urges us to be aware, pollution of the environment between countries and continents, cases of destruction of living beings, soil erosion and desertification processes unfortunately continue. Such ecological disasters, for example, the disaster at the Chernobyl nuclear power plant in the last quarter of the last century, the drying up of the Aral Sea, the nuclear tests near Baikonir, etc., are clear examples.

Main part: This study guide mainly consists of two parts, the first part covers the history of the development of ecological science, external environmental factors, population, biocenoses, ecotism and biosphere concepts,

their theoretical issues, and the second part covers practical issues of ecological science, i.e. natural resources, their use, ecological problems of our planet's air, water shell, agriculture, as well as nature reserves, national parks, archipelago problems and global relations in the field of nature protection. At the end, a list of ecological terms, concepts and used literature is presented.

A brief history of the development of ecology. Biocenosis and its structure. (Biocenology), ecology of ecological systems, ecology of the biosphere. Practical issues of ecology.

It is known that the concept of ecology was introduced into science a century and a half ago, but it can be said that it was created as a science at the first stages of human development.

According to archaeologists, in the images carved on rocks and caves, people were worried about the quality of their houses in primitive times and tried to improve them. Then, over the centuries, ideas about human beings and other living organisms and the surrounding environment - Mother Nature - have been developing in complexity.

Ibn Sina's works total more than 280, of which more than 40 are devoted to medicine, about 30 to natural sciences, 185 treatises to philosophy, logic, ethics and social issues, and 3 treatises to the field of music. He is famous not only as an accomplished poet, but also as the founder of the Ruba'i genre in Persian poetry. His book "Laws of Medicine" has been used as a guideline in the field of medicine for 600 years. His work "Kitab ush-shifo" contains valuable information on such sciences as botany, geology, mineralogy, astrology, mathematics and chemistry. He also wrote down valuable information about underground minerals, earthquakes, and volcanoes. He is one of our great scientists who made a great contribution to the development of world culture with his rich heritage.

The development of science in the world, on the one hand, and the rapid growth of the population on the other hand, had a great negative impact on the biosphere in which we live and the environment that surrounds us in the next hundred years. In this situation, first of all, a number of countries with highly

developed industry and national economy, with a high standard of living of their people, began to impose extremely responsible tasks. As a result, humanity for the first time began to notice the biosphere in which it lives, that is, to speak metaphorically, that the ax is hitting the branch or root of the tree on which it is sitting. That is why advanced representatives of European, American, and Asian continents began to talk through mass media. In conclusion, they fully admitted that people are the main culprits.

In fact, instead of preserving the integrity of nature, as mentioned, various injuries were inflicted on it, and these later began to spread beyond the local and regional boundaries to the national, national and human boundaries. It is important that in order to improve the ecological situation, it is necessary to achieve environmental purity, not to put pressure on nature, to achieve the rule of law, and thus to take measures to prevent and eliminate them. In addition, they unanimously began to study the causes and consequences of the worsening of the ecological situation, and in this regard, they repeatedly turned to the science of ecology. Botany, zoology, microbiology, chemistry, soil science, plant science, and even agriculture have come together to help ecological science in solving the problems facing science and gaining universal importance.

In order to teach young people ecologically, we must always work on ourselves, gain deep knowledge and skills. Only then will we be able to convince the student. In the lesson, it is necessary to explain to students the basic information about ecology in a clear, convincing, simple and understandable way. In this way, not only giving them theoretical knowledge, but attracting their attention to natural phenomena and events, comparing their impressions with the knowledge they have received, directing them to draw appropriate conclusions (of course, logical) requires the skills and experience of the teacher. For this, we need to love the science of ecology, approach it seriously, and have a deeper knowledge system. In this regard, it is important to use the rich experience of teaching in higher educational institutions of our country. Undoubtedly, such experiences exist in our university, Tashkent National University, and universities in Karshi,

Bukhara, Gulistan, Karakalpakstan, Khorezm, and Valley regions. It is gratifying that methodical works and textbooks on the method of teaching ecology, lectures and practical training have been created and are being created. In particular, scientific work is being carried out on environmental issues and problems, most of the students are also doing graduate work in this regard based on the holistic problems of a particular situation, all of which is undoubtedly due to the attention to the science of ecology and the qualified specialists being trained in this regard.

At this point, it should be noted that now the science of ecology is included in the educational programs of higher educational institutions from the lower level, that is, it is considered as the first level of educational and training issues, and teaching is recognized as mandatory. Now the issues of ecological education and training should be carried out not only in educational institutions and primary and secondary schools, but also in all organizations, enterprises and state institutions, and we should inculcate in people an ecological concept and an attitude towards the ecological masses. After all, these are the most urgent tasks in our 21st century

The teaching of ecology in such an order and volume will provide an opportunity to educate future specialists from the point of view of ecological knowledge and for the student to understand more deeply the inextricable connection between the ecological state of the environment and his responsibility as a citizen and specialist in this regard.

This explains that in all of the above cases, in order to maintain the balance between nature, society and man, the environmentalist is required to perform his duties diligently and approach his duties with devotion.

Conclusion: After all, man, as an integral member of both nature and society, is a product of biological and social adaptation. In order for a person to live in these two environments, a source of biological resources is definitely needed. These include, for example, the biosphere system that supports life, the biosphere that is characteristic of human economic activity, and the resources necessary for human development in all aspects. It should be noted that the deterioration of the environment, air and water pollution, soil degradation, humus

depletion, erosion, desertification, salinization and drought processes can also lead to the degradation of countries and their peoples.

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